

Targeting FMS-Like Tyrosine Kinase 3 (FLT3) in Acute Myeloid Leukemia: Novel Molecular Approaches and Therapeutic Challenges

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Abstract: Acute myeloid leukemia (AML), a heterogeneous hematologic malignancy, has generally a poor prognosis despite the recent advancements in diagnostics and treatment. Genetic instability, particularly mutations in the *FMS-like tyrosine kinase 3 (FLT3)* gene, is associated with severe outcomes. Approximately 30% of AML patients harbor *FLT3* mutations, which have been linked to higher relapse and reduced survival rates. Traditional AML treatments employ cytarabine and anthracyclines drugs. Furthermore, the development of *FLT3* inhibitors has significantly improved therapy for *FLT3*-mutated AML patients. For example, the introduction of midostaurin, the first *FLT3* inhibitor, improved patient outcomes. However, resistant AML cell clones continue to pose a challenge to the success of AML treatment.

This review discusses FLT3 kinase, mutations, and role in AML pathogenesis. It explores the molecular mechanisms of FLT3 activation, signaling pathways, and the structure and function of the FLT3 receptor. Current and emerging therapeutic approaches are presented, while highlighting the latest FLT3 inhibitors in clinical use, and strategies to overcome drug resistance. Future directions, including personalized therapies and novel drug designs, are examined to provide updated insights into FLT3-targeted treatments. This comprehensive review aims to guide clinicians and researchers in the development of innovative therapies to improve AML patient outcomes.

Keywords: acute myeloid leukemia; FMS-like tyrosine kinase 3; *FLT3* mutations; FLT3 inhibitors; drug resistance; personalized medicine

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INTRODUCTION

Acute myeloid leukemia (AML) is a heterogeneous hematological malignancy with an poor prognosis despite the extensive progress made in the diagnostic and treatment approaches over the past decade. Moreover, the incidence of cases continues to rise, particularly due to the emergence of AML following prior cytotoxic therapy for a different cancer. A genetically unstable landscape in AML has been described, and mutations in several genes have been linked to favorable or adverse prognosis for patients [1]. During the diagnosis stage, patients are stratified based on cytogenetic and genetic

alterations. Such stratification provides the primary basis for further therapeutic decisions. For more than a half-century, and until recently, the only therapy available comprised a traditional antiproliferative combination of cytarabine with anthracyclines. The link between AML and mutations in the gene encoding FMS-like tyrosine kinase 3 (FLT3) was established in 1997 when Yokota *et al.* identified the internal tandem duplication in the *flt3* gene (FLT3-ITD) as a mutation specific to both myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS) and AML [2]. Mutations in *flt3* were found in 30% of newly diagnosed AML patients and some patients with MDS, and were identified as a clear marker of poor therapeutic outcomes. While the FLT3-ITD occurs with the frequency of 24 % [3], the single point mutations in the activation loop (FLT3-TKD mutations) can be found in about 7 % of AML cases [4,5]. Patients bearing any of these *flt3* mutations show constitutive cytokine-independent FLT3 activation that induces downstream signaling and affects cellular proliferation and apoptosis, leading to enhanced cell survival with inhibited differentiation [4]. Higher relapse rates and decreased overall survival (OS) compared to the patients lacking the mutation, were shown as consequences of such events [6,7]. The development of specific targeted inhibitors against these mutations became a subject of interest for medicinal chemists. Few years after the approval of the first FLT3 inhibitor, midostaurin becoming the pioneering drug to the therapeutic portfolio of AML exerting FLT3 inhibition and achieving a modified prognosis. According to the European Leukemia Net (ELN) classification released in 2018, patients with FLT3-ITD mutations were placed in the adverse-risk group [8]. Nevertheless, only a few years after the introduction of midostaurin, the prognosis of FLT3 mutation-positive patients significantly improved, therefore the ELN 2022 placed patients with FLT3-ITD mutations in the intermediate-risk group [1]. While the FLT3-targeted treatment has significantly improved the prognosis for patients with FLT3 mutations, leading to lower relapse rates and higher OS, some patients can experience clonal evolution of AML cells escaping the therapy, driving the disease to the relapse [9]. For this reason, effective targeting of FLT3 detected at *de novo* diagnosis or during therapy, is still a hot topic among clinicians and presents challenges to medicinal chemists. This review provides a detailed overview of the background behind the FLT3 receptor and its mutation. Our aim is to provide up-to-date information regarding the molecular-biological aspects of FLT3 activation, introducing treatment strategies and an overview of currently available drugs, highlighting novel FLT3-targeting therapeutic approaches.

1 STRUCTURE AND FUNCTION OF FLT3

The mammalian genome contains nearly 60 receptor tyrosine kinases (RTKs), which can be subdivided into 20 different families [10,11]. FLT3 belongs to RTKs, formerly known as STK1 (human stem cell kinase 1), FLK2 (fetal liver kinase 2), or CD135. FLT3 is classified as a class III RTK [12], belonging to the platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF) receptor family, together with PDGFR α/β (platelet-derived growth factor receptor α/β), c-KIT (mast/stem cell growth factor receptor, CD117), and CSF1R (colony-stimulating factor 1 receptor). Class III RTK is pivotal in regulating cellular processes such as growth, differentiation, adhesion, motility, and apoptosis [13,14]. FLT3 is predominantly expressed on the surface of hematopoietic stem cells, and early myeloid and lymphoid progenitor cells [10,15,16], but it is also expressed in the brain and several other tissues as well. FLT3 is involved in hematopoietic cell processes, such as proliferation, differentiation, and survival. FLT3 expression is suppressed when the cells complete the differentiation [16,17]. Mutations in both c-KIT and FLT3 can co-occur in some hematologic malignancies. Such mutations often indicate a poor prognosis and can influence the therapeutic approach, as both c-KIT and FLT3 can be targeted by specific tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs) [18].

1.1 FLT3 LIGAND

FLT3 ligand (FLT3L) acts as a growth factor released by fibroblasts and hematopoietic cells within the bone marrow microenvironment [15]. FLT3L was discovered together with c-kit ligand in the early 1990s, both acting as important hematopoietic factors with unique and nonredundant effects on progenitor and stem cells [19]. The *flt3lg* gene encoding FLT3L was cloned in 1994 by Lyman *et al.*, and was located on human chromosome 19 at the 19q13.3 locus [20]. The crystal structure of FLT3L was elucidated in 2000 [21]. FLT3 exists either as a transmembrane protein consisting of four domains or soluble FLT3L, which is thought to be released into circulation from the cell membrane by protease cleavage. Soluble FLT3L is a non-covalently linked dimer comprising two short-chain α -helical bundles and binds to FLT3 receptor through their *N*-terminal segment.

1.2 FLT3 GENE

The *flt3* gene, encoding the FLT3 receptor, was also discovered and cloned in the early 1990s [12,22–24]. It is situated on chromosome 13 at the 13q12.2 locus. Its expression is primarily observed in hematopoietic stem cells (HSC). In humans, the most primitive self-renewing HSCs exhibit long-term reconstituting activity demonstrating low-level expression of human FLT3 (hFLT3). This expression is upregulated during the early stages of granulocyte/macrophage and lymphoid progenitors, while it diminishes in megakaryocyte/erythrocyte progenitors [25]. Regarding tissue-specific expression, hFLT3 is prominently expressed in the spleen, lymph nodes, and bone marrow under physiological conditions [26].

1.3 STRUCTURAL BIOLOGY OF FLT3

The human *flt3* gene encodes a 993 amino acid protein. FLT3 is initially synthesized as a 110-kDa protein, which is glycosylated in the endoplasmic reticulum to a 130-kDa immature protein rich in mannose, and further processed into a mature 160-kDa protein in the Golgi apparatus, which could be transferred to the cell surface [27,28].

FLT3 is the most distinct class III RTK with several unique features (Figure 1). Class III RTKs share a common structural organization, composed of four domains: an extracellular domain (ED) that consists of five immunoglobulin-like (Ig-like) units, a transmembrane domain (TMD), a juxtamembrane domain (JMD), and a conserved cytoplasmic domain with two tyrosine kinases (TKDs) separated by a kinase insert (Figure 1 B). The ED is composed of five IgG-like domains (D1 – D5), with about 100 amino acids each. A connecting linker joins the ED with TMD, which is a single helix of about 25 amino acids situated within the cell's plasma membrane. JMD, in FLT3, composed of amino acid residues 572–603, connects the TMD to TKD I and TKDII (in FLT3, amino acid residues 604–958). The TKDII is of particular significance as it accommodates the activation loop, a structural element that allows the binding of downstream substrates [29].

The monomeric receptor is inactive, and this inactive state is maintained by the interactions between JMD and TKD, which blocks the ATP binding site [30]. FLT3 activation is induced upon the binding of FLT3L to the ED of the receptor, causing a conformational change (Figure 1A), which enables dimerization, autophosphorylation, and activation of the kinase domains and subsequent activation of the downstream signal transduction pathways [31], which ultimately promotes transcription of genes regulating cell survival, proliferation, and differentiation.

In the ED, the ligand binding is mediated solely by D3, while D2 is not involved (unlike in other class III RTKs). In FLT3, D2 leans against D3 through hydrophobic interaction. Furthermore, the two copies of D1 extend asymmetrically out of the dimer without interacting with the ligand or other parts of the receptor. Unlike the other class III RTKs dimers, the FLT3 complex noticeably lacks homotypic receptor contacts mediated by D4 and D5 [11,14,17].

The JMD located adjacent to the TMD on the cytoplasmic side acts as a regulatory segment, while the JMD of the dormant monomeric form of FLT3 inhibits the catalytic activity of the TKD. The JMD can be divided into three distinct topological segments: the JM binding motif (JM-B), the JM switch motif (JM-S), and the zipper or linker peptide segment (JM-Z). Despite its limited size of only seven residues, JM-B interacts with nearly every structural component involved in the activation/inactivation cycle of FLT3's cytoplasmic domain. JM-B forms a "wedge" that stabilizes the inactive kinase conformation of FLT3 by preventing the N lobe from rotating toward the C lobe to generate the activated kinase fold. The JM-S, a switching motif of 14 residues, is located externally on the C lobe of kinase domains and plays a crucial role as it contains two key tyrosine residues whose phosphorylation status is linked to the activation and regulation of the receptor's enzymatic activity. The JM-Z (11 residues) is located at the C terminus of the JM domain and is associated with the N lobe of kinase domains as it loops around the outside of the N lobe's sole alpha helix. The JM-Z region can undergo large amplitude rotations away from the N lobe by pivoting at its attachment point [32]. Ligand binding to the extracellular domain of FLT3 promotes dimerization of the receptor and concomitant juxtapositioning of the cytoplasmic domains. Once the dimer is formed, transphosphorylation of specific tyrosine residues (Y589 and Y591) on the JM-S region can take place [33]. When one or both tyrosines are phosphorylated, the JM-S cannot fold up properly and position itself next to the C lobe in a manner that maintains the autoinhibited state. Such arrangement is responsible for full kinase activity. The role of the JM-Z is to correctly align and maintain the JM-S in the proper register during and after the transition between activated and inactive states of FLT3. Therefore, the length of the JM-S is critical for proper transitioning between the dormant, autoinhibited monomeric state, and the activated, dimeric state of FLT3 receptor. Unfortunately, this region is prone to internal tandem duplication mutations (FLT3-ITD), which lead to the constitutive activation of FLT3, contributing to the uncontrolled proliferation observed in AML [34]. FLT3-ITD can be found in other hematological malignancies such as MDS, or chronic myeloid leukemia (CML).

TK domains are associated with specific kinase activity. Upon receptor dimerization and activation, these domains undergo autophosphorylation on specific tyrosine residues, creating docking sites for downstream signaling molecules and initiating a cascade of intracellular signaling pathways involved in cell survival, proliferation, and differentiation [35].

A negative feedback loop plays a role in deactivating the FLT3L/FLT3 complex. Upon activation, the dimerized receptor bound to the FLT3L is rapidly internalized and degraded. Alternatively, the kinase activity is negatively modulated by the tyrosine phosphatase that dephosphorylates the JMD. As the phosphatase removes phosphates, the JMD correctly positions around the kinase domain, fitting precisely onto its autoinhibitory site [35].

Figure 1. A – The structure of FLT3 kinase and its activation upon FLT3L binding. Type I FLT3 inhibitors bind to a receptor in active conformation near the activation loop or the ATP-binding pocket. They are active against both FLT3-ITD and FLT3-TKD mutations. Type II FLT3 inhibitors bind to receptors in inactive conformation near the ATP-binding site. They are effective against FLT3-ITD mutations only. **B** – Tertiary structure of FLT3 kinase (PDB ID: 1RJB) [32]. The receptor is shown in cartoon conformation and each region is depicted in a different color. The phosphate-binding loop (blue) is involved in the binding and positioning of ATP for efficient transfer of the phosphate group. An activation loop (purple) conformation determines the kinase's active or inactive state, and undergoes a significant structural change upon receptor activation. α C Helix (green) represents a key component in the kinase's active site that aids in substrate coordination and stabilization.

2 SIGNALING PATHWAYS ACTIVATED BY FLT3

FLT3L and FLT3 interaction causes a series of rapid conformational changes in the receptor, leading to the adoption of a catalytically active form that initially promotes autophosphorylation and homodimerization events (Figure 2). Subsequently, FLT3 exposes binding sites for various adaptor molecules whose docking leads to the activation of mainly PI3K/AKT/mTOR, RAS/MAPK/ERK and JAK/STAT pathways [16,17,36].

2.1 PI3K/Akt/mTOR

The PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling pathway regulates cell proliferation, apoptosis, and cell cycle progression [37,38]. Concerning hematopoiesis, PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling plays an immense role in HSC maintenance [39]. The mechanism by which FLT3 activates PI3K is not fully understood [40]. In general, PI3K is activated directly and indirectly through cooperation with different types of receptors [41]. Signaling through PI3K is highly associated with the subcellular localization of interacting proteins. PI3K is a plasma-associated lipid kinase that converts phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂) to phosphatidylinositol 3,4,5-trisphosphate (PIP₃). PIP₃ recruits lipid-binding proteins to the cell membrane and localizes AKT, activating mTOR and additional downstream pathways [42]. AKT exerts its antiapoptotic and pro-survival effects through several functions. Firstly, it influences various transcription factors (CREB, NF κ B, FOXO), thus promoting either; the expression of antiapoptotic and pro-survival genes or the decreased expression of genes involved in apoptosis induction and cell cycle

arrest. Secondly, AKT directly blocks some pro-apoptotic Bcl-2 family proteins and caspase 9 [43]. Furthermore, AKT enhances the activity of mTORC1, which regulates ribosome biogenesis and promotes the synthesis of proteins needed for cell growth and division. mTORC1 also influences cellular metabolism by promoting lipid and nucleotide synthesis and inhibiting autophagy [44]. The activity of PI3K is negatively regulated by the PTEN protein [37], and the relationship between AKT and mTORC1 is also tightly controlled by feedback mechanisms [45]. The PI3K pathway is active (or it can be activated) in either FLT3-WT, FLT3-TKD, or FLT3-ITD, and it has been suggested that PI3K and ERK are more active in FLT3-WT than FLT3-ITD [40].

2.2 PI3K/Akt/mTOR IN AML

Hyperactivation of the PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway is crucial in the development of various malignancies, including leukemias [37]. In blast cells from AML patients, PI3K/Akt/mTOR signaling is frequently activated, abnormally promoting cell proliferation and survival [42,46,47]. PI3K shows a low mutation rate in AML, although the four isoforms are overexpressed in AML cells [47]. About half of all AML cases have mutationally activated signaling in pathways upstream of PI3K (ITD/length mutation or point mutation of *flt3*, activating mutations in the KIT tyrosine kinase, mutations in *RAS*) [46]. The activity of PI3K is negatively regulated by the PTEN protein with lipid phosphatase activity. Although mutations of *PTEN* are uncommon in myeloid leukemias, PTEN is often functionally inactivated in AML and CML through transcriptional silencing and protein inactivation [37,48].

2.3 MAPK PATHWAY (RAS/RAF/MEK/ERK)

Ras-Raf-MEK-ERK pathway responds to many external stimuli that regulate cell proliferation and death. In normal hematopoiesis, ERK signaling is suggested to be involved in the regulation and maintenance of early myeloid commitment of HSCs and is required for optimal expansion of progenitors during myelopoiesis. Further, it is essential for granulocytopoiesis, monocytopenoiesis, and the final maturation of erythrocytes [49].

Conformational changes caused by FLT3L binding to FLT3 initiate the MAPK signaling cascade. FLT3 binds the adaptor protein GRB2, mediating GDP dissociation and GTP binding to Ras to activate the Ras/MAPK cascade [50,51]. Structural studies identified tyrosine residues Y589 and Y599 within the JMD as phosphorylation sites important for ERK activation in FLT3-WT [40]. Activated ERK triggers diverse proliferative signaling via numerous transcription factors [52] and regulation of Bcl-2 family proteins [53].

The proteins of the Ras/MAPK pathway exhibit substantial crosstalk with the PI3K pathway and stimulate cell proliferation and survival [42]. It remains unclear whether the MAPK pathway, PI3K pathway, or a combination of both primarily regulates FLT3-mediated signaling cascades. Gaining a deeper understanding of these interactions would provide valuable insights into the spatial and temporal coordination between these signaling pathway dynamics [40].

2.3.1 MAPK pathway (Ras/Raf/MEK/ERK) in AML

Ras pathway mutations commonly emerge as cooperating mutations in leukemogenesis. Similar to PI3K, activated Ras signaling frequently occurs in the context of upstream FLT3 activity. Mutations in the *RAS* genes, particularly *NRAS* and *KRAS*, are found in a significant subset of AML patients. It was shown that approximately 11.9% of AML patients have mutations in the *NRAS* gene, while about 6.1% have mutations in the *KRAS* gene. These mutations occur in approximately 16.9% of all AML cases [54]. In addition, as Ras activity is GTP-dependent, mutations that inactivate Ras GTPases will also lead to constitutive Ras activation [42]. As a result of mutations in FLT3 or self-mutated Ras, downstream

effectors such as MAPK are highly activated, leading to uncontrolled cell growth and differentiation, which are related to the progression of the malignant tumor [50]. Pharmacological inhibition of the RAS has shown potential in overcoming FLT3 inhibitor resistance in FLT3-ITD AML [55].

2.4 JAK/STAT5

The JAK/STAT signaling is essential for cell survival, proliferation, and differentiation. This signaling pathway acts as a crucial signal transmitter for the cytokine receptor superfamily, playing a pivotal role in the hematopoiesis of myeloid and non-myeloid cells and immune regulation [56]. The JAK-STAT signaling pathway is initiated through ligand binding to cognate transmembrane receptors. This binding induces conformational changes in the receptors, triggering the subsequent activation of associated JAKs. This, in turn, provides a docking site for STAT proteins, leading to their phosphorylation and dimerization, which ensures the release of STAT from the receptor and its translocation into the nucleus. In the nucleus, STAT proteins regulate the transcription of genes coding pro-proliferative and antiapoptotic proteins by directly targeting DNA regulatory elements [57,58]. In mammals, four JAK proteins and seven STAT proteins have been identified. Based on the ligand, the receptor and their tissue specificity, distinct combinations of STATs and JAKs are activated [58].

In the hematopoietic system, JAK-STAT signaling tightly orchestrates survival and self-renewal of HSC, hematopoiesis, and proliferation [58]. Various STAT5 inhibitors are currently undergoing phase I or II clinical trials for the treatment of several hematological malignancies [59]. FLT3-WT activates STAT5 indirectly via the ERK pathway. STAT3 has been shown to play an important role during myeloid homeostasis, differentiation, and proliferation. Due to its ability to block myeloid differentiation, its crucial role during leukemogenesis is highlighted [58].

2.4.1 JAK/STAT in AML

STAT3 and STAT5 are constitutively activated in 44–76% of AML patients [58,60]. Activation of STAT5 in AML often occurs downstream of receptor tyrosine kinases, such as in FLT3-ITD mutations, leading to persistent STAT5 activation. This results in the promotion of genes involved in cell cycle progression and antiapoptotic genes, enhancing the proliferation and survival of leukemic cells while maintaining an undifferentiated state. Furthermore, activated STAT5 enhances the expression of NADPH oxidase (NOX) enzymes, leading to elevated production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [61].

Accumulating evidence suggests that dynamic changes in the intracellular localization of FLT3 and maturation of this glycoprotein affect the control of its downstream signaling pathways. FLT3-WT is mainly localized on the cell surface, whereas FLT3-ITD is retained longer in the ER-Golgi network [17]. If FLT3-ITD is localized at the membrane, it strongly activates the MAPK and PI3K pathways, while endoplasmic reticulum anchored FLT3-ITD aberrantly activates STAT5 with no ability to upregulate other signaling pathways such as MAPK and PI3K [62]. Thus, FLT3-ITD can activate the same pathways as wild-type FLT3, albeit in an aberrant manner. Although much is known about the STAT5 pathway, the exact mechanism by which it is activated in FLT3-ITD remains unclear. Structural studies identified tyrosine residues Y589 and Y591 within the JMD as phosphorylation sites important for this activation. Strong evidence suggests that STAT5 is directly phosphorylated by FLT3 instead of JAK, thus, bypassing JAK activation [40,63].

Figure 2. Downstream signaling pathways in FLT3 activation depict the differences between the physiological and constitutively activated FLT3 receptor.

OXIDATIVE STRESS AND FLT3 SIGNALING

Several lines of evidence have documented that FLT3-ITD mutation is closely linked with increased ROS production in AML cells [64]. FLT3-ITD mutations result in the activation of NOXs, particularly NOX2 and NOX4 [65]. This constitutive activation of NOXs generates higher levels of ROS. It has been shown that 65% of primary AML blasts produce increased extracellular superoxide compared to control group, with some samples showing 100-fold greater levels, although no correlation with AML molecular subtype was found [66].

As a secondary signaling molecule, ROS plays multiple roles in FLT3-ITD AML. Moderate levels of ROS can act as pro-survival signals, promoting cell proliferation. However, high concentrations of ROS can cause oxidative damage and increase the likelihood of erroneous DNA repair [67,68]. Notably, quiescent AML leukemia stem cells (LSCs) generally have lower ROS levels than cycling LSCs and bulk AML cells [65]. Despite this, quiescent AML LSCs still experience oxidative DNA damage even without high ROS levels. This damage enhances genomic instability and drives the genetic evolution of LSCs, likely providing them with competitive advantages [69].

NOX2 is highly expressed in myeloid cells and is a major source of ROS in these cells. NOX2 is present in phagocytes, including neutrophils and macrophages, where NOX2-derived ROS are essential for the respiratory burst, a rapid release of ROS used by phagocytes to kill pathogens. In the hematopoietic system, NOX2 normal function is required for proper myelopoiesis. The deficiency of NOX2 or the cooperating proteins significantly perturbs the normal balance of blood cell production and limits the self-renewal potential of HSC [70]. NOX2-derived ROS have been shown to promote AML cell survival and resistance to daunorubicin [71].

FLT3-ITD signaling through STAT5 promotes the expression of NOX4, leading again to increased ROS formation [61,72]. Conversely, the activation of NOX can further enhance STAT5 signaling, thus creating a positive feedback loop that exacerbates disease progression. Another mechanism for constitutive activation of NOX is linked with the stabilization of one regulatory subunit for NOX1-4 via FLT3-ITD activated Akt.

Oxidative stress is also linked with the activity of protein tyrosine phosphatase (DEP-1), which controls FLT3 dephosphorylation and regulates FLT3 activation. DEP-1 dephosphorylates specific tyrosines in TKD domain and turns off the FLT3 signaling. However, DEP-1 activity is sensitive to oxidative stress, and excessive production of ROS oxidizes its catalytic cysteine residue [72]. Also, the FLT3 receptor contains cytosolic cysteine residues, presenting thiol groups as potential targets for biologically significant post-translational modifications and interactions with metabolic molecules. These modifications contribute to conformational changes, acting as a molecular switch in the signaling cascade of the receptor. As a result, the interplay between oxidative stress and ROS, which influences the thiol groups within the FLT3 receptor, along with possible post-translational modifications, emerges as a plausible mechanism by which cells finely tune and regulate FLT3 receptor signaling. This regulatory framework may lead to the hyperactivation of signaling cascades crucial for the progression of AML [40].

3 FLT3 INHIBITORS IN CLINICAL USE

The primary goal for the treatment of AML patients is to eradicate or at least control the disease. This outcome is accomplished ideally by inducing a complete remission with initial intensive therapy, which consists of cytarabine and anthracycline also known as “7+3” regimen. Typically, the regimen is followed by consolidation and/or maintenance efforts to deepen the remission and maximize the response duration [1]. To optimize therapy outcomes, genetic analyses are performed to identify the best treatment option. Currently, FLT3 kinase inhibitors represent a well-established standard in the first-line therapy for patients with FLT3-mutant AML. After complete remission (CR) has been attained, patients are consolidated with regimens that include intermediate-dose cytarabine. Patients considered unfit for intensive chemotherapy can receive hypomethylating agents (HMAs), mostly azacitidine and the BCL2 inhibitor venetoclax, which was recently found to significantly improve clinical response and median OS in this group of patients [73]. At clinical progression, it is important to consider the potential for clonal evolution and the emergence of molecular targets not detected at diagnosis. These include, among others, also emergence of new FLT3 mutation or expansion of previously detected FLT3-ITD or FLT3-TKD point mutation clones. The stability of FLT3 mutations throughout the AML therapy is known to be particularly variable as a new FLT3 mutation can be identified in up to 20% of previously FLT3-wild-type patients [74]. Conversely, a patient with FLT3-mutated disease at diagnosis can relapse with an FLT3-negative clone, especially after the FLT3-containing therapeutic regimen [75]. If the FLT3 mutation persists or is newly identified, targeting FLT3 becomes a critical component of the otherwise limited therapeutic options.

3.1 FLT3 INHIBITORS IN INITIAL AML THERAPY

The first generation of FLT3 inhibitors is represented by tandutinib (CT53518), lestaurtinib (CEP-701), sunitinib (SU11248), midostaurin (PKC412), and sorafenib (BAY 43-9006), all showing inhibition potency against FLT3, albeit with varying degrees of specificity and off-target effects [76–80].

Primary treatment with midostaurin gained FDA and EMA approval in 2017 for use in conjunction with intensive “7 + 3” chemotherapy, and was validated by the RATIFY trial (Table 1). This phase 3 study encompassed patients with FLT3-ITD and FLT3-TKD mutations, regardless of allele ratio. The results of the study indicated a notable extension in OS with midostaurin compared to the placebo group, albeit CR rates were not significantly different between both groups [81]. Later UNIFY trial conducted in FLT3-negative AML patients showed that the clinical effect of midostaurin is directly related to FLT3-positive setting [82]. As the first targeted small molecule treatment option for AML in decades [83], midostaurin represents a significant milestone in modern AML therapy. Its introduction has spurred a wave of clinical trials for other targeted compounds, extending beyond FLT3-targeted treatments. Since then, FLT3 inhibitors have become an indispensable part of AML treatment [84]. Moreover, ongoing clinical trials seek to establish the potential role of FLT3 inhibitors in the treatment of pediatric patients.

Sorafenib is a multitarget tyrosine kinase inhibitor examined in combination with 7 + 3 in the SORAML trial, providing mixed outcomes. The trial involved AML patients, with or without FLT3 mutation, and exhibited improvement in event-free survival (EFS) and relapse-free survival (RFS) with the addition of sorafenib. However, there was no significant improvement in OS. Even though patients with FLT3-ITD mutation in the sorafenib arm showed improved OS and RFS; this positive outcome was not supported by statistical significance [85]. Sorafenib treatment was furthermore linked to significant toxicity, including diarrhea, bleeding, and cardiac events. Moreover, further evaluation of sorafenib in combination with intensive chemotherapy in FLT3-ITD mutation patients did not reveal significant EFS or OS benefits [86]. The long-term follow-up to the SORAML trial showed statistically significant

improvement of EFS and RFS, while the impact on OS remained below the significance threshold [87]. Second-generation FLT3 inhibitors like gilteritinib (ASP2215), quizartinib (AC220), and crenolanib (CP868596) were designed to be more specific to the FLT3 receptor and are endowed with higher efficacy, kinase selectivity, and less pronounced side effects [88–92].

Among others, a second-generation FLT3 inhibitor, quizartinib, demonstrated a significantly improved median OS compared to the placebo, with similar adverse event proportions in both groups [93]. Incorporating quizartinib into standard chemotherapy, followed by continued monotherapy, represents an effective and generally well-tolerated treatment option for adults with newly diagnosed FLT3-ITD-positive AML, as evidenced by the QuANTUM-First trial, which put the ground for gaining approval to this novel FLT3 inhibitor by FDA and EMA in 2023. No direct comparative study to date has evaluated the impact of FLT3 inhibitors combined with intensive chemotherapy on OS. However, a recent network meta-analysis found no significant differences in efficacy among midostaurin, quizartinib, and sorafenib [94].

Gilteritinib, when combined with anthracycline and cytarabine induction followed by cytarabine consolidation, exhibited promising results in a phase 1 study involving newly diagnosed AML patients regardless of FLT3 mutation status [95]. Among patients with *de novo* diagnosed FLT3 mutation, gilteritinib achieved a composite CR rate of 81.6%, with notable clearance of FLT3-ITD mutation. The median OS for the entire study cohort was 35.8 months. Adverse events leading to gilteritinib discontinuation were observed in 12.7% of patients, with transaminases being the most common grade ≥ 3 adverse events [96]. Currently, a phase 3 study is underway to compare gilteritinib with midostaurin in combination with 7 + 3 chemotherapy, aiming to further evaluate its efficacy in first-line AML treatment (NCT04027309).

3.2 FLT3 INHIBITORS FOR PATIENTS NOT ELIGIBLE FOR INTENSIVE CARE

Combining FLT3 inhibitors with HMAs, including azacytidine or decitabine, and/or venetoclax is slowly becoming a standard of care for newly diagnosed elderly or unfit FLT3 AML patients who are not eligible for intensive chemotherapy [84]. The results are compromised by relapses that occur very often despite high initial CR rates. Combining FLT3 inhibitors with HMA/venetoclax has the potential to significantly improve outcomes, especially for fragile patients including elderly, and polymorbid patients [97]. Furthermore, the treatment is not burdened by cumulative dose organ toxicity which represents a critical treatment barrier for anthracyclines. Prospective trials evaluating FLT3 inhibitors, in addition to HMA/venetoclax, have been conducted in upfront and salvage settings showing promising outcomes. Studies have reported high composite CR rates and minimal residual disease (MRD) negativity in newly diagnosed, relapsed, and refractory (R/R) FLT3-positive AML patients treated with FLT3 inhibitors added to decitabine/venetoclax [98,99]. Sorafenib exhibited a promising response rate in previously untreated elderly patients when combined with azacytidine, while the combination was generally well-tolerated [100]. Preliminary outcomes of triple therapy with decitabine, venetoclax, and quizartinib in R/R FLT3-ITD-positive AML have shown a high CR/CRi (CRi stands for complete remission with incomplete hematologic recovery) rate and a median OS of 7.6 months [101]. Furthermore, data on azacytidine and venetoclax with gilteritinib have demonstrated outstanding CR rates in newly diagnosed FLT3-positive AML [99].

3.3 MAINTENANCE IN RELAPSED AND REFRACTORY SETTINGS

Despite the recommendation to offer allogeneic stem cell transplantation (Allo-SCT) to suitable patients with FLT3-ITD mutation, high relapse rates persist post-Allo-SCT [102]. It was also described that FLT3 mutation could occur in relapsed patients who do not have FLT3 mutation at the time of their initial diagnosis [103–106].

Sorafenib and midostaurin have been investigated in phase II trials as monotherapy maintenance post-Allo-SCT, with sorafenib demonstrating substantial OS and disease-free survival benefits in the SORMAIN trial, possibly attributed to mechanisms beyond FLT3-ITD inhibition [107]. According to this study, patients with undetectable MRD before HCT and those with detectable MRD after HCT can benefit the most from the administration of sorafenib. This was further supported by the published results of this phase II/III study that showed a reduced incidence of relapse in patients on sorafenib maintenance therapy [108]. The extended 5-year endpoints of the SORMAIN trial showed improved OS (HR = 0.55; p = 0.011) in the sorafenib maintenance cohort [109]. The trials evaluating midostaurin maintenance did not show statistically significant improvements in event-free or overall survival [110]. Recent studies have demonstrated that gilteritinib treatment following allo-SCT improved RFS. While the benefit in the general population did not reach statistical significance, patients with detectable MRD exhibited a significantly reduced relative risk (hazard ratio 0.515) of relapse [111]. Establishing criteria for the indication of Allo-SCT followed by FLT3 inhibitor maintenance therapy is crucial. These criteria should encompass an evaluation of the patient's overall health status, FLT3 mutation status, prior use of FLT3 inhibitors before transplantation, availability of compatible donor tissue, and the patient's prognosis [84,112].

In cases of R/R AML, midostaurin monotherapy did not provide a survival benefit. Two phase 3 clinical trials published in 2019 compared quizartinib and gilteritinib to salvage chemotherapy in patients with R/R FLT3-positive AML. Quizartinib offered an OS advantage over salvage chemotherapy, with a median duration of composite complete remission of 12.1 weeks. A higher proportion of patients treated with quizartinib subsequently underwent Allo-SCT compared to the chemotherapy group [113]. Gilteritinib monotherapy showed a median OS of 9.3 months, compared to 5.6 months with salvage chemotherapy, with a median duration of remission of 14.8 months [114]. Despite higher response and Allo-SCT rates with quizartinib, gilteritinib monotherapy resulted in more durable remissions and improved OS. Interestingly, only three days after quizartinib was approved in Japan, the FDA raised concerns about the study design and results, leading to its non-approval for use in R/R settings [115]. For the abovementioned reasons, gilteritinib remains approved for monotherapy of R/R FLT3-positive AML by the FDA from 2018 and the EMA from 2019; it is considered the first-line option among FLT3 inhibitors for R/R settings [84]. The data obtained from the gilteritinib phase 3 ADMIRAL trial was further confirmed in a population pretreated by midostaurin and/or intensive chemotherapy [116].

Table 1. Overview of phase II and III clinical trials with FLT3 inhibitors.

[1] TRIAL	DRUG REGIMEN	PHASE	CLINICAL SETUP	PRIMARY ENDPOINT	MAJOR SECONDARY ENDPOINT(S)	REFERENCE
NCT02927262	Gilteritinib vs. placebo	II	Allo-SCT maintenance	RFS (24.02 vs. 15.84 months; p = 0.163)	OS, EFS	[117]
NCT01883362 (RADIUS)	Midostaurin vs. standard care	II	Allo-SCT maintenance	RFS probability in 18 months (0.76 vs. 0.89; p = 0.2655)		[110]
NCT00651261 (RATIFY)	Midostaurin vs. placebo	III	Newly diagnosed	OS (74.7 vs. 25.6 months; p = 0.009)	EFS, CR, DFS	[81]
NCT02668653 (QuANTUM-First)	Quizartinib vs. placebo	III	Newly diagnosed	OS (31.9 vs. 15.1 months; p = 0.0324)	EFS, CR	[93]
NCT02039726 (QuANTUM-R)	Quizartinib vs. salvage chemotherapy	III	Relapsed/refractory	OS (27.0 vs. 20.4 weeks; p = 0.0185)	EFS	[113]
NCT02421939 (ADMIRAL)	Gilteritinib vs. salvage chemotherapy	III	Relapsed/refractory	OS (9.3 vs. 5.6 months; p = 0.0004)	CR/CRh, EFS	[114]
NCT03512197 (UNIFY)	Midostaurin vs. Placebo	III	Newly diagnosed FLT3-neg	EFS (5.98 vs. 5.88 months; ns.)	OS	[82]
NCT02474290 (SORMAIN)	Sorafenib vs. placebo	II/III	Allo-SCT maintenance	1-year relapse incidence (7.0 vs. 24.5 %, p = 0.001)	OS, safety	[108]
NCT00893373 (SORAML)	Sorafenib vs. placebo	II	Newly diagnosed	EFS (9 vs 26 months; p = 0.01)	OS, RFS	[118]

Allo-SCT – allogenic stem cell transplantation, CR – complete remission, DFS – disease free survival, EFS – event free survival, OS – overall survival, RFS – relapse free survival

3.4 RESISTANCE TO FLT3 INHIBITORS

Despite considerable progress in AML treatment achieved by introducing FLT3 inhibitors into clinical therapy, drug resistance has emerged and the respective mechanisms have been described for most of them. In general, the persistence of leukemic stem cells (LSC) in the bone marrow arises from their high adaptability to the surrounding niche and the development of resistance mechanisms [119]. The transfer of exosomes is involved in reprogramming the bone marrow compartment by the FLT3-mutated leukemic cells, which suppresses normal hematopoiesis, favoring the survival of LSCs [120]. Bone marrow-derived stromal cells show significant inhibition of chemotherapy-induced apoptosis in

AML and the stromal cell-derived factor-1 (SDF1)-CXCR-4 axis enhances the FLT3 inhibitor resistance [121]. The clonal evolution of FLT3-ITD mutations seems responsible for resistance to treatment with FLT3 inhibitors and disease progression. As shown in the RATIFY study, only 59% of the AML patients who were treated with midostaurin achieved complete remission, after which half of them relapsed [81].

At the molecular level, a secondary point mutation in the already mutated FLT3 gene has been identified as a primary cause of acquired resistance to sorafenib, imposing significant challenges on AML treatment [122]. Subsequently, the mutations F621L, A627P, F691L, and Y842C in FLT3-ITD were identified as the cause for varying levels of resistance to FLT3 inhibitors, resulting in ineffective inhibition of FLT3 autophosphorylation and signaling through MAPK, STAT5 and AKT in the mutants [123]. Relapsed AML patients carrying FLT3-ITD mutation and treated with quizartinib typically experienced secondary point mutations in the activation loop residue D835 (D835Y/V/H/E/N) [124,125]. Considering the enormous diversity of FLT3-ITD mutations, the location and amino acid sequence of ITD can be one of the primary resistance causes through altering the protein conformation followed by activation of alternative downstream signaling pathways.

The FLT3-ITD variant FLT3-ITD627E was found to be causative for primary cellular resistance to the first approved FLT3 inhibitor midostaurin and is characterized by consecutive and inhibitor-independent overexpression of the antiapoptotic protein MCL-1 [126]. A single amino acid substitution at N676K within the FLT3-ITD conferred resistance to midostaurin in clinical settings [127]. Besides on-site FLT3-located mutations, midostaurin treatment can be accompanied by the induction of mutations in JAK family kinases [128]. Interestingly, cells with the FLT3 A848P mutation, which causes secondary resistance to sunitinib and sorafenib, remain sensitive to midostaurin [129]. In contrast to quizartinib and midostaurin, the secondary resistance against gilteritinib is rarely caused by FLT3-TKD point mutations. Gilteritinib has thereby shown high activity against newly acquired point mutations in FLT3, such as D835 [130]. In contrast, such changes can induce acquiring off-target mutations (*NRAS*, *KRAS*) in Ras/MAPK signaling pathway. A recent study by Joshi *et al.* identified specific time-dependent and FLT3-dependent behavioral patterns in a leukemic cell line exposed to gilteritinib. The study found that early-resistant cells undergo metabolic reprogramming, grow more slowly, and depend on Aurora kinase B (AURKB). In contrast, late-resistant cells are characterized by the expansion of pre-existing *NRAS* mutant subclones and continued metabolic reprogramming [131].

The knowledge of the mechanisms underlying the development of resistance to FLT3 inhibitors leads to designing new concepts for improving the response to FLT3 inhibitors and reducing the development of resistance in AML [132–134]. Among these stand-out combinatory therapy concepts and new molecules targeting FLT3 while changing the AML bone marrow microenvironment seems a promising approach as well.

4 STRUCTURAL INSIGHTS AND DRUG DESIGN

4.1 STRUCTURAL BIOLOGY OF FLT3 AND ITS INHIBITORS

FLT3 inhibitors are divided into two categories based on their binding mechanisms and the conformational state of the FLT3 kinase they target: Type I and Type II inhibitors (Figure 1A). This classification is based on their binding affinity to the DFG (Asp-Phe-Gly) loop within the kinase domain. The phosphorylation status of Tyr residue distinguishes between active DFG-in and inactive DFG-out conformations [135]. Type I inhibitors bind to the active conformation of the FLT3 kinase and are anchored to the ATP-binding site and its proximity, regardless of the DFG status. As ATP-binding sites are well-conserved among kinases, type I inhibitors usually suffer from poor selectivity. On the

contrary, type II inhibitors bind to the inactive conformation of the FLT3 kinase and reside close to the hydrophobic area of the FLT3, resulting in their higher selectivity over type I inhibitors. Besides, type II inhibitors are unable to inhibit activated kinases in the DFG-in conformation. Type I inhibitors account for midostaurin, sunitinib, gilteritinib, lestaurtinib, and crenolanib, whereas sorafenib and quizartinib belong among type II inhibitors. Type I inhibitors are effective against both FLT3-TKD and FLT3-ITD mutations while type II inhibitors act exclusively for FLT3-ITD species. An overview of the FDA-approved and clinically investigated FLT3 inhibitors and their classification, is outlined in Table 2.

Table 2. List of FDA-approved and clinically investigated FLT3 inhibitors, their characterization, and efficacy in certain FLT3 mutations. Drug sensitivity is compared to IC₅₀ values against native FLT3 kinase, where efficacy is sorted as S (sensitive; improvement or no drop in IC₅₀ values related to native kinase), Int (intermediate; IC₅₀ values are equal or decreased up to two-fold related to native kinase), and R (resistant; IC₅₀ values are reduced more than two folds). N.d. stands for not determined. Data were collected from (Aikawa et al., 2020; Barry et al., 2007, 2007; Eid et al., 2017; Galanis et al., 2014; Kampa-Schittenhelm et al., 2013; Karaman et al., 2008; Klaeger et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2017; Levis et al., 2002; S. Mori et al., 2008; Nguyen et al., 2017; O'Farrell et al., 2003; Schittenhelm et al., 2009; C. C. Smith et al., 2015; Weisberg et al., 2017; Yee et al., 2004)

Drug	FDA status/clinical trial NCT	Inhibitor Type	Drug sensitivity			
			FLT3-ITD	FLT3-D835Y	FLT3-ITD-D835Y	FLT3-ITD-F691L
midostaurin	approved in 2017	I	S	S	R	R
sunitinib	Three clinical trials in total with the most advanced phase II (NCT01620216 - completed 2017)	I	S	R	R	R
lestaurtinib	Three clinical trials in total with the most advanced phase II (NCT00079482 - study completed 2010; NCT00030186 - study completed 2003);	I	S	Int	S	n.d.
gilteritinib	approved in 2018	I	S	S	Int	R
crenolanib	11 clinical trials with the most advanced phase III (NCT02298166 - terminated in 2020; NCT03250338 - recruiting; NCT03258931 - recruiting)	I	S	S	Int	R
sorafenib	47 clinical trials with the most advanced phase III (NCT01371981 - active; NCT02665065 - active; NCT06073730 - active)	II	S	R	R	R
quizartinib	approved in 2023	II	S	R	R	R

4.2 RATIONAL DRUG DESIGN STRATEGIES

FLT3 inhibitors are part of an effective modern therapeutic strategy for the treatment of AML. The success of FLT3 inhibitors as clinical candidates encouraged numerous developmental studies focusing on designing new drug lead compounds. These strategies employ a range of medicinal chemistry approaches. In the following subchapters, the most advanced drugs that have led to potent FLT3 inhibitors will be highlighted. We do not provide an extensive and in-depth overview of FLT3 inhibitors campaigns that generated highly potent preclinical drug candidates. For these reasons, readers are kindly referred elsewhere [150–154].

4.2.1 Core scaffolds in the design of FLT3 inhibitors

Beyond the mentioned classifications, FLT3 inhibitors can also be stratified based on their molecular structural features (Figure 3). Despite the well-conserved region of the ATP-binding pocket, a relatively wide variety of compound's structural cores that accommodate the binding site of FLT3 can be found [150,152,154,155]. Among them, staurosporine, a natural product isolated from *Streptomyces* sp., is endowed with indole[2,3-*a*]carbazole moiety that can be used as an antineoplastic agent, with a proposed mechanism of action involving protein kinase C (PKC) inhibition [156]. Midostaurin (*N*-benzoylstaurosporin) and lestaurtinib are the analogs to staurosporine targeting FLT3. Pacritinib, another inhibitor entering clinical trial phases 2 and 3, belongs to the large family of 4-aryl-2-aminopyrimidine macrocycles acting as a combined FLT3/JAK2 inhibitor [157]. In an effort to optimize pacritinib potency, several diaminopyrimidine or diaminopyrazine derivatives were investigated [158]. Gilteritinib also belongs to the group of pyrazine carboxamides [159]. Several purine derivatives were also developed as FLT3 inhibitors; however, only HYML-122 entered clinical trials in China [154]. Representatives from the 3,4- or 3,5-disubstituted pyrazole families, especially FN-1501, obtained approval for orphan drug status from the FDA in 2019 as an FLT3/CDK2 inhibitor [154,160]. Quizartinib is a diarylurea-based compound recently approved by the FDA and EMA. Crenolanib is a member of benzimidazoles. Although crenolanib is not yet FDA-approved, there are currently three phase 3 trials ongoing, and the results from phase 2 trials demonstrated promising activity in newly diagnosed *FLT3*-mutated AML patients [161,162].

Figure 3. Chemical structures of the most effective and the most frequently found basic core structures and their corresponding final products as efficient FLT3 inhibitors.

4.2.2 FLT3 inhibitors with dual activity to avoid resistance acquisition

There are currently two strategies applied to countermeasure the quick resistance development to selective FLT3 inhibitors: the combination strategy and the discovery of multitarget drugs [153,163]. Dual inhibitors are designed to simultaneously target another kinase, such as JAK2, CDK4, MEK, Mer, Pim, SYK, Fes, AKT, PDGFR, Aurora B, and TOPK, among others, to mitigate the resistance occurrence [153]. These co-targets are chosen with a focus on their pathway relationships to ensure coverage of additional downstream regulators. As a result, the therapeutic effect of the drug should be significantly improved, and the issues associated with combinatory therapy are reduced. On the other hand, the discovery of such agents is often limited by their toxicity, selectivity, PD, PK, etc.

Midostaurin is considered a multitarget inhibitor with significant activity on Spleen tyrosine kinase (SYK), which is expressed in most hematopoietic cells as an essential partner to FLT3. As SYK overexpresses and transactivates FLT3-ITD, it enhances resistance to selective FLT3 inhibitors. Midostaurin reaches a similar affinity towards both targets. Indeed, the inhibitory efficacy for SYK is $IC_{50} = 21$ nM, and the binding affinity for FLT3 lies also in the nanomolar range ($K_d = 11$ nM) [90,140,164]. Although efficacy against these two kinases is the most profound, midostaurin inhibits other targets such as PKC, the vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2 (VEGF-R2), PDGFR, and c-kit [165]. In contrast, gilteritinib exerts a less promiscuous profile, plausibly resulting in less frequent side effects and reduced toxicity. Gilteritinib effectively inhibits both targets FLT3 and AXL with subnanomolar IC_{50} values of 0.29 and 0.73 nM, respectively [159]. AXL is another receptor tyrosine kinase frequently overexpressed in various cancers, including AML [166]. Considering the structural similarity of another member of the class III receptor tyrosine family, PDGFR, it is not surprising that FLT3 inhibitors are often active against the other members [167]. Crenolanib is a good example of such

property, revealing inhibition towards several other targets with K_d values of 0.7 and 2.1/3.2 nM for FLT3 and PDGFR α/β , respectively [168,169].

4.3 ALTERNATIVE APPROACHES TARGETING FLT3

FF-10101 is the only currently investigated FLT3 irreversible inhibitor, forming a covalent bond with the cysteine residue at 695 of FLT3. This unique binding manifested high selectivity and efficacy against all types of FLT3 kinases [169]. Recently, a phase 1 study in relapsed and refractory was evaluated and the recommended dose for the phase 2 study was established to 75 mg twice daily. The dose-limiting toxicities were diarrhoea and QT prolongation [170].

There are also other approaches beyond the therapy based on small molecules targeting FLT3 (Figure 4). Great effort has been made by stimulating the immune system to combat leukemic cells. Accordingly, there are two main options to do so, namely chimeric antigen receptor T cells (CAR-T cells) and antibodies. Therapy with CAR T-cells was approved by the FDA as a treatment for Large B-cell lymphoma in 2017 [171]. Since then, immunotherapy approaches for AML have been steadily increasing. Currently, 57 clinical trials are investigating CAR T-cell therapy in AML patients. However, only four of these trials specifically examine the effects of CAR T-cells on FLT3 (as listed on [ClinicalTrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov)).

A highly expressed FLT3 antigen (70-100 %) in hematologically malignant patients is an attractive target for CAR-T cell therapy [172]. Jetani *et al.* engineered FLT3 targeting CAR-T cells with cytotoxic activity against either wild-type or mutated receptor variants [173]. An apparent synergistic effect was observed with FLT3 inhibitor crenolanib, which enhanced the overall response rate and OS compared to monotherapy in mice [174]. Li *et al.* developed dual-target CAR-T cells combining FLT3 single-chain fragment variable (scFv) and natural killer group 2 member D ligands (NKG2DL) [175]. NKG2DL is a marker significantly expressed in AML cells compared to normal cells, and its concentration is increased by the administration of gilteritinib [176]. Different FLT3-CAR-T cells were generated and characterized in several other studies [177–179].

FLT3 receptors are present not only in AML cells but also in HSCs and myeloid progenitor cells, which can result in adverse effects during treatment. Here, we provide a brief overview of novel approaches to reducing hematotoxicity. Potent FLT3-CAR-T cells were transduced with two rituximab mimotopes, which mimic the epitopes where the desired antibody binds. This modification allows the CAR-T cells to be depleted by rituximab, an already approved monoclonal antibody. The data shows that four out of five mice that received rituximab regained hematopoietic progenitor cell levels comparable to those in the untreated control group, after CAR-T cell therapy [180]. The insertion of the FLT3L sequence to the CAR-T cells, instead of targeting scFv, is another promising approach to minimize off-target cytotoxicity. The cytotoxic effect correlates with the concentration of FLT3L, indicating that FLT3 receptors' binding capacity is a reason for lowered effectivity and off-target cytotoxicity [181].

Bispecific T-cell Engager (BiTE) molecules targeting FLT3 receptors is another approach to lower CAR-T cell hematotoxicity in AML patients. BiTE molecules create a bridge between specific antigens in tumor cells and CAR-T cells, allowing the immune system to effectively reach and combat the cancerous cells. The molecular weight of the BiTEs can affect the pharmacokinetic profile, especially elimination by kidneys. The benefit of BiTE molecules compared to CAR-T cells lies in their lower toxicity and stockpiling ability, which is crucial for leukemic patients who require immediate treatment. A couple of BiTE molecules entered phase 1 clinical trials, but the trials were terminated without further specification [182,183].

Monoclonal antibodies (mAB) are another option in the treatment of AML. The high-affinity, fully human anti-FLT3 neutralizing antibody IMC-EB10 was introduced nearly two decades ago. Phase 1 clinical trial on 24 patients with R/R AML confirmed the safety profile, but the mAB failed to achieve

clinical efficacy [184]. To address the lack of effectiveness in clinical settings, modifications were made, resulting in the engineering of antibody 4G8SDIEM, later termed FLYSYN. Preclinical data demonstrated antibody-dependent cellular toxicity, a favorable toxicity profile, and FLT3 specificity, all of which appeared promising enough to warrant the initiation of clinical trials. The toxicity profile and effectiveness of 4G8SDIEM monotherapy in AML patients with MRD were evaluated in a Phase I clinical trial [185]. A response rate of 46% in patients and the occurrence of only mild to moderate adverse events prompted the advancement of 4G8SDIEM to a Phase II clinical trial [184]. There are other mABs targeting FLT3 with promising preclinical data awaiting to show their efficacy in clinical settings [186–188].

4.4 GENE THERAPY AND GENE EDITING

Due to the genetic heterogeneity of AML, the engineering of safe and reliable gene therapy is challenging. Although gene editing is a growing field, there is not much data on gene therapy for AML. The results of the only study identified on FLT3 show that gilteritinib response can be enhanced by editing genes encoding FLT3. In contrast, a significantly worse response to sorafenib treatment was observed [189]. There are still many challenges to be overcome before gene therapy can establish its role in treating heterogeneous and rapidly progressing hematological disorders like AML.

4.5 OTHER OPTIONS TO INDIRECTLY TARGET FLT3 VIA SMALL MOLECULES

4.5.1 Heat shock protein 90 inhibition

Inhibition of the heat shock protein 90 (Hsp90) molecular chaperone leads to destabilization of its client proteins and FLT3 receptor degradation [190]. Improved cytotoxic effect of 17-AAG HSP90 inhibitor in FLT3 mutated cells was achieved in combination with cytarabine or midostaurin [191,192]. The effect of 17-AAG in FLT3-WT remains inconclusive, given the reports with contradictory results [193]. Due to its lack of specificity, 17-AAG has entered numerous clinical trials across various cancers; yet only a few trials have focused on AML patients, and none have evaluated the effect of 17-AAG in combination with an FLT3 inhibitor [194]. The ability to degrade FLT3 mutated receptors via Hsp90 inhibition has also been described in green tea polyphenols. Interestingly, these molecules were cytotoxic for cell lines regardless of their FLT3 mutation status, but they specifically degraded receptors with FLT3 mutations [195].

4.5.2 Histone Deacetylase Inhibitors

Histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibitors can degrade FLT3 via induced acetylation of Hsp90. Compounds LAQ824 and its analog panobinostat (LBH859) were able to induce apoptosis in nanomolar concentrations in AML cell lines [196,197]. Nevertheless, the lack of specificity and insufficient safety profile in clinical settings in elderly patients with AML do not provide a promising future for HDAC inhibitors in AML therapy [198]. Wang *et al.* recently synthesized 63 novel FLT3/HDAC dual inhibitors showing the promising results *in vitro* [199]. Additionally, other effective dual inhibitors were introduced by Chang *et al.* [200]. Taken together, this approach can lead to novel potent anti-AML drugs.

4.5.3 Targeting FLT3 degradation

4.5.3.1 Proteolysis targeting chimeras (PROTACs)

FLT3 targeting can be achieved using proteolysis targeting chimeras (PROTACs). PROTACs are heterobifunctional molecules that simultaneously bind to an E3 ubiquitin ligase and the target protein

[201,202]. The major advantage of PROTACs is their ability to inhibit cell growth more effectively while having fewer off-target effects. This binding facilitates the ubiquitination and subsequent degradation of the target protein. In fact, FLT3-targeting PROTACs could work through at least two mechanisms; direct inhibition and induced degradation of the kinase. This approach could be even more effective as PROTACs act as catalytic agents and can function repeatedly, promoting sustained degradation of the kinase over time. Preclinical studies have shown promising results for novel PROTACs targeting FLT3-ITD, both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [203–205].

Burslem *et al.* demonstrated that although a quizartinib PROTAC analogue slightly loses efficacy *in vitro* and *in cellulo* compared to the parent compound quizartinib, it exhibits a much more restricted kinase interactome. Additionally, the PROTAC drug showed superior growth inhibition in mouse models [206]. Similar results *in vitro*, *in vivo* or both were also shown in other studies transforming potent FLT3 inhibitors into PROTACs [205,207–213]. Moreover, dovitinib-designed PROTAC effectively induced the degradation of both targeting proteins FLT3-ITD and KIT [207].

4.5.3.2 Proteasome inhibitors

The proteasome inhibitor bortezomib has been reported to degrade FLT3-ITD and induce cytotoxic effect in AML cells by triggering autophagy [214]. Furthermore, bortezomib showed efficacy against quizartinib-resistant cell lines, suggesting its ability to overcome resistance to FLT3 inhibitors through a different mechanism of action. Currently, the effect of bortezomib, an already approved treatment for multiple myeloma, in combination with sorafenib, is being evaluated in *de novo* AML patients with FLT3-ITD, with results expected in late 2027.

4.5.3.3 RET inhibitors

Rearranged during transfection (RET) is a receptor that promotes the proliferation and survival of AML cells. RET inhibitors may indirectly affect the mechanistic target of rapamycin complex 1 (mTORC1)-regulated autophagy, which is responsible for the inhibition of autophagy, including FLT3-ITD [215]. There is a correlation between FLT3 and RET protein expressions. Furthermore, treatment with RET inhibitors vandetanib and danusertib decreased the cell viability in FLT3 mutant cell lines and AML patient samples. The combination of vandetanib and FLT3 inhibitor crenolanib significantly increased apoptosis and reduced cell viability [216]. PLM-101 is dual inhibitor of both FLT3 and RET. The first report showed an antileukemic effect by induced apoptosis, while other mechanisms, such as cell cycle arrest or inhibition of PI3K and Ras/ERK signaling pathways, were also described. Basic pharmacokinetic parameters and the toxicity profile were tested in mice, and no findings were identified that would discourage further clinical trials of the molecule [217].

4.5.3.4 Inhibitors of deubiquitinase

The natural way of protein degradation leads through the ubiquitin-proteasome system. Ubiquitin-specific protease 10 (USP10) is deubiquitinase that inhibits this system and prevents the degradation of the FLT3 receptor. Therefore, USP10 is another potential target that can be inhibited to support the degradation of FLT3. Interestingly, USP7 inhibitors HBX19818 and P22077 enhanced the degradation of FLT3 in a dose-dependent manner with greater specificity to FLT3-ITD in AML cell lines, including a cell line resistant to midostaurin [218]. Similarly, novel USP10 inhibitor WU-5 showed a cytotoxic effect in AML cell lines with FLT3 mutation, including cell lines resistant to FLT3 inhibitor crenolanib with no or minimal effect in cell lines without this mutation. Additionally, the synergistic effect of WU-5 and crenolanib is caused by the inhibition of the USP10 and FLT3 signaling pathways [219].

Figure 4. Therapeutic FLT3 targeting: FLT3 can be inhibited by small molecule FLT3 inhibitors, but the AML cells can also be distinguished by monoclonal antibodies or CAR-T cells that target FLT3 receptors. This leads to immune system response and, in the case of CAR-T cells, direct cell killing. Another target

uses the knowledge of FLT3 receptor stabilization by Hsp90. Destabilization of FLT3 can be done by HSP90 inhibitors and HDAC inhibitors. The ability of PROTAC to bind E3 ubiquitin ligase to FLT3 causes FLT3 proteasomal degradation. The inhibition of USP10, FLT3 deubiquitinase, by USP10 inhibitors is another way to enhance FLT3 protein degradation. The ability of proteasome inhibitors to induce autophagy causes FLT3 degradation, the same effect observed with inhibitors of RET proto-oncogene, which is responsible for autophagy arrest. Hsp90 – Heat shock protein 90; Ub – ubiquitin, FLT3 – FMS-like tyrosine kinase 3; PROTAC - Proteolysis targeting chimeras, HDACi – Histone deacetylase inhibitors, RET – receptor tyrosine kinase encoded by “rearranged during transfection” proto-oncogene.

5 CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

AML is a heterogeneous hematologic malignancy characterized by the clonal proliferation of myeloid precursors with impaired differentiation. Among the various genetic mutations associated with AML, FLT3 mutations are one of the most prevalent and are linked to poor prognosis and an increased risk of relapse. The invention of FLT3 inhibitors has been a critical advancement in targeting these mutations and improving patient outcomes. These inhibitors have shown potential not only in frontline therapy but also as maintenance therapy post-chemotherapy or post-HSC transplantation. Research is ongoing to optimize the duration and combination of maintenance regimens for maximum benefit.

The introduction of FLT3 inhibitors has significantly improved clinical outcomes in AML therapy. First-generation inhibitors, including midostaurin and sorafenib, have demonstrated modest but significant efficacy in patients with FLT3 mutations. These agents laid the groundwork for the development of more targeted therapies. Second-generation FLT3 inhibitors, such as gilteritinib, quizartinib, and crenolanib, offer greater selectivity and potency in treating FLT3-mutated AML, addressing some of the limitations observed with first-generation drugs.

Despite the progress made with FLT3 inhibitors, resistance remains a significant hurdle in AML treatment. Resistance can be categorized into two types: primary and secondary. Primary resistance is driven by intrinsic factors present before treatment, such as stromal protection and clonal heterogeneity. Secondary resistance develops after initial treatment, often due to acquired mutations that hinder the effective binding of FLT3 inhibitors. Secondary mutations in the FLT3 gene, such as those affecting the D835 residue, can reduce the binding affinity of FLT3 inhibitors, particularly type II inhibitors like quizartinib and sorafenib, which target the inactive conformation of FLT3.

The selective pressure exerted by FLT3 inhibitors can lead to the emergence of resistant subclones, which may either lack FLT3 mutations or acquire additional mutations that activate alternative survival pathways. Among them, mutations in the RAS/MAPK and PI3K/AKT/mTOR pathways have been identified in patients who relapse after treatment with FLT3 inhibitors. As a result, research efforts are focused on developing third-generation FLT3 inhibitors that are more selective, potent, and capable of overcoming existing resistance mechanisms. These inhibitors aim to target both the active and inactive conformations of FLT3 and address mutations that confer resistance to current therapies.

The landscape of AML therapy is rapidly evolving, with personalized therapy gaining more attention as a strategy to improve clinical outcomes. Tailoring treatment plans based on the genetic and molecular profiles of AML patients, including the integration of FLT3 inhibitors with other targeted agents or conventional chemotherapy, can enhance efficacy and mitigate resistance. For example, combining FLT3 inhibitors with other therapeutic agents, such as venetoclax (a BCL-2 inhibitor) or HMAs like azacitidine or decitabine, has shown great promise in enhancing efficacy and overcoming resistance. These combinations have demonstrated synergy in clinical settings, offering a new avenue for treating R/R AML.

To conclude, FLT3 inhibitors play a pivotal role in managing FLT3-mutated AML, with significant advancements improving patient outcomes. However, challenges such as drug resistance and disease

relapse necessitate ongoing research and innovation. The integration of novel inhibitors, combination strategies, and personalized treatment approaches holds promise for further improving outcomes in AML patients. Continued exploration of the molecular mechanisms underlying FLT3 mutations and resistance will be vital in refining therapeutic strategies and achieving long-term remission in AML.

Conflict of Interest

Authors declare no competing interest.

Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

During the preparation of this work, the authors used the ChatGPT 4o tool to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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List of Abbreviations

Allo-SCT, allogeneic stem cell transplantation; AML, acute myeloid leukemia; AURKB, Aurora kinase B; BiTE, Bispecific T-cell Engager; CAR-T cells, chimeric antigen receptor T cells; CML, chronic myeloid leukemia; CSF1R, colony-stimulating factor 1 receptor; CR, complete remission; CRi, complete remission with incomplete hematologic recovery; DEP-1, protein tyrosine phosphatase; DFG, Asp-Phe-Gly loop; ED, extracellular domain; EFS, event-free survival; ELN, European Leukemia Net; FLK2, fetal liver kinase 2; FLT3, FMS-Like Tyrosine Kinase 3; FLT3-ITD, FLT3 internal tandem duplication mutations; FLT3L, FLT3 ligand; hFLT3, human FMS-Like Tyrosine Kinase 3; HDAC, histone deacetylase; HMA, hypomethylating agent; HSC, hematopoietic stem cell; Hsp90, heat shock protein 90; STK1, human stem cell kinase 1; Ig, immunoglobulin; JM-B, JM binding motif; JM-S, JM switch motif; JM-Z, zipper or linker peptide segment; JMD, juxtamembrane domain; LSCs, leukemia stem cells; mAB, monoclonal antibody; MDS, myelodysplastic syndrome; MRD, minimal residual disease; mTORC1, mechanistic target of rapamycin complex 1; NKG2DL, natural killer group 2 member D ligands; NOX, NADPH oxidase; OS, overall survival; PDGF, platelet-derived growth factor; PDGFR α/β , platelet-derived growth factor receptor α/β ; PIP2, phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate; PIP3, phosphatidylinositol 3,4,5-triphosphate; PKC, protein kinase C; R/R, relapsed and refractory; PROTACs, proteolysis targeting chimeras; RET, rearranged during transfection; RFS, relapse-free survival; ROS, reactive oxygen species; RTKs, receptor tyrosine kinases; scFv, single-chain fragment variable; SDF1, stromal cell-derived factor-1; SYK, Spleen tyrosine kinase; TMD, transmembrane domain; TK, tyrosine kinase domain; TKIs, tyrosine kinase inhibitors; VEGF-R2, vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2

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